

SAFEGUARDING OUR SILENT PARTNERS: A UNIFIED VISION FOR ANIMAL WELFARE, HUMAN WELL-BEING, AND ENVIRONMENTAL CONSERVATION FOR A SUSTAINABLE TOMORROW

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ABSTRACT

Animal health exerts a multifaceted impact on human health and nutrition, agriculture, the economy, biodiversity, and the complex interplay within biological systems. Understanding animal health from a broad perspective necessitates multidisciplinary approach. Working in a resource-constrained environment renders teamwork essential and impactful. There is plenty of evidence to suggest that collaborative teamwork and interdisciplinary approach has greatly improved the outcomes of animal health across the world. We can carry this forward and intensify this approach for the wellbeing of animals to have a healthy animal population and healthier humans.

KEYWORDS: One health, CARG, zoonosis, animal conservation

INTRODUCTION

Animals contribute vitally to the complex interplay between biological systems. They are an integral part of the food chain, serve as pollinators, promote nutrient cycling, disperse seeds, and regulating the populations of numerous plant and animal species. Animals have been a vital component of human growth and civilization, serving roles such as feeding us, carrying our loads to providing us clothing, protectors, emotional support as pets. Owing to their vital role in the ecosystem and their contribution to human existence, safeguarding their health and habitat is one of our soul responsibilities.

ANIMAL HEALTH AND FOOD SECURITY

The human diet is omnivorous, indicating that animals are essential sources of nutrients for humans. Animal products are rich in protein and are significant sources of essential amino acids. Vitamin B12, and vitamin D3 are largely obtained from animal products in our diet. Therefore, safeguarding animal health and better animal husbandry practices contribute to the improvement of food security. Achieving this goal is particularly arduous in India due to its rural and unorganised environment. Veterinary practitioners and livestock inspectors are focused

on animal healthcare, the implementation of animal health initiatives, and the capacity building of farmers. However, the care given to population ratio is abysmal, resources are limited and infrastructure is under developed. Healthy, sustainable, and profitable techniques have not permeated grassroots levels because the sector is largely informal and unorganised, and farmers lack basic animal rearing know-how.

THE PRODUCTIVITY PARADOX: INDIA'S LIVESTOCK UNDER STRAIN

India stands as the world's largest producer of milk, with milk production experiencing a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 5.85% over the past nine years. This may sound impressive but India possesses the world's largest cattle population; however, the production per cattle is extremely variable and mostly low, resulting in a ranking of 48th in milk exports. Unavailability of pastures, Unhygienic and overcrowded Shelters, nutritional deficiencies, poor healthcare and higher disease burden has plagued the cattle, sheep, goat and pigs industry in rural India. The poultry industry is also challenged with frequent disease outbreaks, viz Ranikhet and Influenza, high feed cost, an extremely hot and humid climate and low access to veterinary care.